

DEVELOPMENT OF SPEAKING COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS THROUGH AN INNOVATIVE APPROACH IN TEACHING THE STORY OF NAVOIY "ZAYD ZAHHOB"

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ABSTRACT: This scientific article reflects on the methods of forming the elements of speech competence through an innovative approach in teaching academic lyceum students the grace of Alisher Navoi's literary heritage, the skill of choosing words, and the use of artistic image tools. It is shown that the charm of the masterpieces of art and speech art in Navoi's epic reveals the inner, hidden abilities of the students, and encourages them to think creatively and come up with creative ideas.

KEY WORDS: competence, listening comprehension, speaking, reading comprehension, writing, Zayd Zahhab, ruler, ship, idol, pagan.

Adoption of the new version of the Law "On Education" in the Republic of Uzbekistan and its introduction into the educational process caused radical changes in the republic's education. In the civilization of the world, science and technology is developing so much that its development affects the development of literature, science, art, and culture of every nation. In Uzbek literature, reading and analyzing classic examples of written literature, born under the influence of folk oral creativity, has become a hobby of every reader. Reading the work of classical authors and listening to it does not happen directly. It is known that A. Navoi, a poet and statesman, has a special place with his indelible mark in the history, his unique creativity in the world of poetry, and the possessor of a tender soul. This heritage makes us understand literature and poetry, feel the intricacies of thought in them, and understand the meaning of life. In accordance with the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4910 on "Selecting talented young people for academic lyceums", in order to develop education focused on the formation of certain competencies in students, teaching the lyrical heritage of A. Navoi in academic lyceums and instilling its true essence into the minds of students through new innovative methods. An attempt was made to highlight the beauty of the arts.

According to the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 646, the elements of speech competence: listening comprehension, speaking, reading comprehension, writing are the main goals of today's education.

Navoi's epic "Sabayi Sayyor" purifies the soul, serves to form a high spiritual world in the human body, and plays an important role in the creation of a perfect person. Minds familiar with Navoi always strive for goodness, share goodness and beauty with others. In the prose description of the epic "Sabayi Sayyor", the story of the stranger from the second climate is taught to the students, first of all, the content of the text is closely introduced. Then logical questions are asked based on the text. At the end of the lesson, before giving the test questions, they are given excerpts from the story "Zaydi Zahhab" and continue the content. This method of "Feedback" strengthens the concentration of attention even of the student who is not paying attention to the lesson process, quickly and easily understands the topic. His logical thinking, his interest in learning, studying and acquiring a profession will increase. Let's get acquainted with the short text of the story "Zaydi Zahhab" from the epic "Sabayi Sayyor".

During the time of Shah Jamshid, there lived a skilled jeweler in the country of Rum. His rare works were known to the people. In the royal palace, this jeweler performed the duties of owner and treasurer. Every gold and silver taken from the mine was brought to him. Because of this profession, he was called Zaydi Zahhab. He was also engaged in medicine and engineering. Day and night, he was the close interlocutor of the king and the main physician of the capital.

Zayd's days were spent in luxury, he considered the king's wealth as his own, but he was dishonest with the trust and did not hesitate to betray the king's property. Shah praised Zayd. No one could blame him, even if any of his sins were revealed to the king, he would not pay attention to him. If Mabodo paid attention, Zayd would use his craft and make wonderful tools, quickly angering the king.

One day, when Zayd came to the king and told him that two thousand batmans of gold would be needed for his throne, the king agreed, took the gold, took it to his office, and started working. Zayd tried to finish the throne in one year. This strange throne had eight legs, four above and four below. There were four talking parrots on the four lower stems, and four peacocks on the higher stems. The staircase of this throne, decorated with dur-u-lalls, also had eight legs, and it was designed in such a way that when the king wanted to ascend the throne, the legs lowered and overlapped one another. let him achieve his goals, let this throne be for him forever." At that moment, four peacocks spread their feathers and cast a shadow on the king's head like Huma bird. In which direction

the king wanted to go, the throne started walking with a slight gesture. This is probably what people call "takhtiravon" - a walking throne.

The king throws a party. The king will raise the reputation of Zaydi Zahhab, a master craftsman. But some artisans who were aware of Zayd's actions knew that the throne was supposed to be made of gold only, but silver was used along with gold. And the fraud master believed that even if the king realized his betrayal, he would not destroy this magnificent throne. Realizing the evil intentions of his enemies, Zayd, although he was afraid, believed in the king's attention to him. At this time, his enemies will think of a way to convey the secret to the king. They find two parrots that look like parrots on the throne, and they teach one of them: "The throne is a fake", and the other "The master is a traitor". They give a lot of money to the one who guards the throne and take them as partners, and in the early morning they exchange the two parrots.

In the morning, when the king ascended the throne, the trained parrots still spoke. Shah was surprised by this and said, "Whoever did this, he is a person who knows about Zayd's work. Because he was afraid of the master, he conveyed his guilt to me through the language of birds. "It is very easy to determine the truth of this case," he thinks, and when he takes a piece of gold in his hand and slightly bends one of the legs of the throne, it becomes clear that silver has been used for the gold base. Knowing about this betrayal, the king cut off his love for Zayd, took away his property, put himself in chains and threw him in prison. This dungeon consisted of a pit with a narrow mouth but a wide bottom. It was absolutely impossible to escape from him.

Zayd was given two bowls of water every day. The master who committed fraud thought that one day he might be thrown into prison, so he always carried a dagger with ego under his shirt, prepared in advance. Zayd finds a way to escape from the dungeon. Every day, when he took bread and water, he would put the bread aside, dig up the soil with a dagger, and use the water to make a bed. The master who cut off the chain from his feet with his ego lived only by the heat of the bread. Every day he would wait for water, and when he got it, he would continue his work. Although the madori was drying up day by day, the zina was also getting higher every day. After several months of difficulty, the ladder finally reached a hole at the mouth of the dungeon, on which a heavy stone was pressed. Zayd digs a hole in the bottom of the rock with his dagger and escapes from the hole. Realizing that if the king finds out, he will be caught and killed, Zayd often walks to Farang.

The jailers inform the king that the prisoner has escaped. Realizing how he escaped from prison, the ruler is amazed by Zayd's tricks. At this time, Zayd, heading towards the country of the Farangs, reached the city of Qustantania. There was a temple outside the city and it was full of people. Entering it, Zayd found out that everything was decorated with gold and jewels, all the walls were decorated with precious stones, and they were closed at night and opened for the people to pray. As for me, I have my eye on the king's gold," he thinks, pretending to be an idolater, and in no time learns the prayers and rituals performed by the infidels. He prayed day and night, expressed his devotion to every idol, and demonstrated the strength of his faith. This kind of trickery makes the people of the temple fool. Zayd's status is increased, and the temple's discretion is completely in his hands. He begins to carry out the trick he has devised.

He sees a cave in the mountain by the sea. During the trip, he made friends with a couple of fellow believers. Zayd searches for the two of them and instructs them to find the inside of the cave: "What tools are needed for jewelry, quickly find them and bring them secretly into the cave." After his companions brought these tools, when Zayd al was sleeping, he and his companions would come to the cave and make iron figures similar to idols, plates and candlesticks in the temple, cover them with gold, replace the real precious stones with fake ones, and take the gold plates and candlesticks to the cave and hide them. None of the people of the temple will find out about these tricks. After all the gold items have been exchanged in this way, Zayd asks the people of the temple to allow him to return to his homeland. They cry out that such a blessed one is leaving them. And Zayd said, "I didn't want to be separated from you either." Unfortunately, my mother died and left behind a lot of wealth, and I have no other heirs. He says, "I will go and receive all the wealth, then I will return to the idols and spend all my wealth on the idol." The people of the temple put their heads at his feet and say "Come safely to your country" and collect many gifts for him. Zayd took them and began to place the idols inside the cave in bags. Putting each idol in a sack, he fills a total of fifty sacks with idols. He also puts gold plates and lamps in sacks and secures them by placing cloths between them. Entering a large ship, he secretly transports all the wealth accumulated in the cave to the ship. He also brings the gifts of the people of the temple to the ship. Stepping onto the ship, Zayd looked at the pagans and said: "I wrote a letter and hid it in the temple. You will find it in front of the idol of Lot. It has something to say about you. Everything is useful for you," he says, and orders the ship to sail. As

the ship was leaving, the people of the temple found the letter and began to read it while they were crying. In the letter, Zayd wrote down everything he had done. All the words in the letter were clearly true. A riot begins among the infidels.

At this time, Zayd reaches the coast of the country of Rum. The king of Rome is sick and lying in bed. In the previous years when this patient had an attack, Zayd would cure him by giving him a medicine he had prepared. After the doctor ran away, after a few moments, this disease began to torment the king again. No one can find a cure for him, and the king's pain is getting worse. Repenting of the punishment given to Zayd, the ruler remembers his physician when the pain increases.

When Zayd went to the beach, he heard about this incident and took all his belongings home, secretly walked inside the city, put the chains he had cut on his hands and feet during the escape, and fell into that deep dungeon. Zindonban learned that Zayd had appeared and quickly informed the king. The ruler was happy and ordered to "bring him to me quickly" and sent him abundant gifts, expensive clothes and his own horse.

When they brought them to Zayd, he did not leave the prison and said, "I have suffered a lot during this time because of the anger of the king. I will pay ten times more gold for that treachery. Another point is that the king, trying to break the idols of the farangs and to satisfy himself in the matter of religion, raised an army twice, but he could not achieve his goal. I will break their idols and give their gold to the king's treasury, I will scatter all my jewels from his head, I will quickly heal his severe pain. I have only one condition: let the king put chains on the legs of my enemies and bring them to me and deliver them to my beloved. Because if I go to the king's palace now, they will definitely attack me. Therefore, if I don't achieve this goal, I won't quit," he answers. Zayd's words are used as an excuse and he orders them all to be captured and thrown into the dungeon. Zayd gives up his place in the palace to them, goes out and puts on the colorful clothes sent by the king, goes to the palace and kisses the king's threshold and shows respect. When the king recovered completely, he poured out all the gold and jewels he had brought in front of him. The astonished king could not believe his eyes. Then he asks, "Tell me what happened." Zayd tells all the events. The king was pleased with his story and sent the presented wealth to the treasury and gave him as much as a gift.

According to the king's decree, each of the idols is divided into a hundred bribes and distributed among the religious people. After that, the king orders

everyone to wear golden clothes. Because gold makes people laugh like saffron. After some time, by the order of the king, the inhabitants of the prison were also released. Those who escaped also started to laugh at their clothes. People laugh at them.

When Bahram heard this story, he was happy and asked about the stranger's homeland and ancestors. "My country is the property of Rome, my work is medicine and wisdom. The son of Zayd, whom I mentioned, will be my father. The purpose of my coming here is to serve you. Thank God, I have reached my goal," the stranger answers. When the king heard this, he appointed him as a nadim, and Bahram, enjoying the story, went to sleep and did not wake up until the sun rose.

After the students are fully introduced to the text, the text is divided into 4 to 12 parts. White and red cards are distributed through the "autofocus method". Through these cards, red card holders are suddenly stood up and asked questions based on the text. After asking 10-12 quick questions, texts divided into parts by the "Autofocus method" are given and asked to continue the story or what happened before this story, the student who answers gets points, the student who fails to answer is not punished, but no points are given. In this way, the lesson ends with the test questions. In this case, all students will receive the points that belong to them. All will fully master the subject, regardless of whether they get high or low marks.

With his works and deep thoughts, Navoi can surprise the reader of today's time and touch the sensitive heartstrings. In the process of working on the text of the "Sabayi Sayyor" epic, the student's speech competence such as writing, reading comprehension, speaking, and listening comprehension is formed. In this, of course, the dictionary of Navoi eras will help a lot. May all of us be accompanied by the grace and delicacy of Navoi's works.

List of used literature:

1. Law of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education". - T.: 2020. September 3-2.
2. Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4910. – T.: December 3, 2020, Appendix 3, Clause 3
3. Decision No. 646 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the introduction of the national test system for assessing the level of knowledge of general education subjects". - T. : 2020. October 12.
4. Alisher Navoi. A perfect collection of works. Volume XX. Volume 10. "Khamsa". "Sabayi Sayyor". - T.: 1993.

5. Tokhliyev B., Karimov B., Usmanova K. Literature. textbook. 11th grade.- T.:
"National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan". 2017. Page 177

